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Indian Major Carp Fisheries of the Ganga River Basin: Challenges, Stakeholder Perceptions, and Strategies for Viability

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Indian Major Carp Fisheries of the Ganga River Basin: Challenges, Stakeholder Perceptions, and Strategies for Viability

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Abstract

The Indian Major Carps (IMC) form the ecological and economic backbone of riverine fisheries in the Ganga River Basin. However, these fisheries face growing challenges from hydrological alterations, habitat degradation, pollution, overfishing, invasive species, and climate variability. This study examines the status, vulnerabilities, and governance dynamics of IMC fisheries using a participatory and experiential framework that integrates stakeholder perspectives, field observations, and institutional dialogues. Findings reveal that IMC catches and seed availability have declined sharply due to altered river flows and ecological stress, directly threatening the livelihood security of traditional fisher communities. The study identifies complex governance asymmetries, where decision-making remains concentrated among policy and infrastructure institutions, leaving fishers marginalised from management processes. Despite these constraints, existing enablers, such as cultural preference, high market value, awareness initiatives, and river ranching programmes under Namami Gange, provide opportunities for ecological recovery and livelihood resilience. The paper argues for adaptive co-management strategies that blend scientific insights with traditional ecological knowledge, strengthen fisher participation in decision-making, and promote cross-sectoral integration of fisheries within Ganga River governance. Sustaining IMC fisheries demands an inclusive, ecologically grounded, and socially just approach to secure both biodiversity and fishers well-being.

Keywords Indian Major Carps • Ganga River Basin • Riverine fisheries • Governance • Fisher livelihoods • Adaptive co-management

गंगा है हमारी शान
रोहू, कटला, मृगल है इसकी जान
प्रदूषण से रहती है ये परेशान
फिर भी माने सबको समान
साफ़ रखो इसका यह पवित्र नाम,
यही बनाता हमारी धरती महान।

*Ganga is our nation's pride,
Rohu, Catla, Mrigal inside.
Pollution gives her constant pain,
Yet she treats all lives the same.
Keep her sacred name alive,
On her strength our earth will
thrive.*

1. Introduction

Fisheries in tropical lowland rivers play a vital role in sustaining livelihoods and ensuring food security for millions of people worldwide (Welcomme, 2008). The River Ganga is India's national river and is very important because it supports the lives and economies of many communities along its banks. Stretching over 2,525 km, the Ganga flows through diverse topographies and ecological zones, nurturing a rich array of floral and faunal biodiversity throughout its course (Dwivedi et al., 2014; Montana et al., 2011; Imran et al., 2015; Tripathi et al., 2017). Its basin, measuring 860,000 sq. km, is the world's most populous, extending across 11 states and covering nearly 26% of the nation's landmass (Das and Tamminga, 2012). From a water resources standpoint, the Ganga basin covers about 30% of India (Das et al., 2022).

Fish and fishery resources are pivotal in improving social and economic status as well as providing substantial employment opportunities (García-Lorenzo et al., 2024). The Ganga River system supports about 10-13 million riverine fishermen, and fishing is the main occupation for fishers, contributing approximately 70% to the total family income along the Bhagirathi-Hooghly stretch of the Ganga (Kumar, 2018; Pandit et al., 2019). According to the Govt of India Census, there are a total of 3,795 fishing villages in the Ganga River stretch, covering five states and 47 districts (Govt of India Census, 2011).

Ganga riverine fisheries are characterised by a small-scale nature, a multi-species composition, and the use of diverse gear types, collectively supporting around 215 fish species. Among these, the Indian Major Carps (IMCs), Catla (*Labeo catla*), Rohu (*Labeo rohita*), and Mrigal (*Cirrhinus mrigala*), form the backbone of the fishery. In the middle stretches of the Ganga, IMCs contribute nearly 60-70% of the total catch, making them culturally preferred, nutritionally essential, and economically indispensable (Sarkar et al., 2012). Traditional breeding and nursery grounds around Varanasi, Patna, and Bhagalpur are considered IMC-rich zones.

The Ganga River system has witnessed a drastic reduction in the landing of IMC over the past several decades. Both the catch quantity and species composition of fish and fisheries have undergone significant changes between 2000 and 2018, mainly due to alterations in the river's hydrological regime and ecology, as well as several anthropogenic activities such as dam construction, pollution, overfishing, invasion by exotic species, and climate change. At Allahabad, the average contribution of IMC to the total catch declined from 38.09% during 1956-1967 to only 15.00% during 2005-2018 (Jha et al., 2020).

Urgent efforts are necessary for the propagation and conservation of IMC, as it originated in the Ganga River system. Maintaining a viable population of IMC would help restore ecological balance while simultaneously supporting the livelihood security of thousands of fishers along the riverbanks, as these species are highly valued in the market. To achieve this, it is imperative to evaluate the threats undermining their sustainability from the perspectives of key stakeholders, including fishers, policymakers, and conservation managers. Such an approach not only provides a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted challenges facing carp fisheries but also highlights potential pathways for inclusive, sustainable, and equitable management of the Ganga River system.

1.1 Objectives

This study was conducted to address the increasing challenges and improve the long-term sustainability of Indian Major Carp fisheries in the Ganga Basin, with the following specific objectives:

- The aim is to assess the status and advancements in the fisheries of Indian Major Carp in the Ganga Basin.
- To methodically document stakeholder perspectives on the key challenges affecting IMC fisheries.

- To examine the governance, ecological, and socio-economic elements that influence the sustainability of fisheries.
- To propose adaptable management strategies and policy pathways focused on achieving long-term sustainability.

2. Methodology

Our study adopted an experiential and participatory learning approach to capture diverse stakeholder perspectives on IMC fisheries in the Ganga Basin. The methodology combined field-based interactions, group discussions, and institutional workshops to document emerging threats to vulnerability and identify pathways to viability in IMC fisheries.

2.1. Data collection

The survey process was grounded in direct engagement with fishing communities and other key actors. The NMCG team conducted extensive conversations with fishers, community leaders, and fisheries department officials to understand their perceptions of ecological, economic, and governance-related challenges related to IMC. Focus group discussions (FGDs) were held with different categories of stakeholders, enabling us to gather a broad spectrum of insights on coping, adaptive, and transformative strategies.

2.2. Observations

Based on the theoretical framework, notes, and observations, a thematic analysis approach was employed. Observation in the selected fishing stretches includes fishing practices, market linkages, and community-level institutions that contextualise stakeholder narratives. These immersive interactions were complemented by a one-day stakeholder workshop organised at ICAR-CIFRI, titled “*Inland Small-Scale Fisheries in the Ganga River Basin: Transitioning from Vulnerability to Viability.*” The workshop brought together fishers, fisheries department officials, researchers, and civil society representatives to collectively deliberate on the vulnerabilities facing IMC fisheries and identify the potential solutions.

2.3. Reporting and knowledge sharing

Community feedback and validation sessions were conducted across key IMC fishing zones and related villages along the Ganga River to ensure inclusive representation of field perspectives. Open conversations with fishers and local organisations made it easier for people to think about the results together. Insights from these sessions were consolidated into this working paper to identify the key drivers influencing IMC fisheries, the changes resulting from these drivers, and the existing enabling systems supporting IMC management in the river.

The research process was based on direct interaction with fishing communities and other important players. Researchers conducted extensive conversations with fishers, community leaders, and fisheries department officials to understand their perceptions of ecological, economic, and governance-related challenges. Focus group discussions (FGDs) were held with different categories of stakeholders, enabling us to gather a broad spectrum of insights on coping, adaptive, and transformative strategies.

We contextualised stakeholder narratives by observing fishing practices, market linkages, and community-level institutions during field visits to selected fishing stretches. These immersive interactions were complemented by a one-day stakeholder workshop organised at ICAR-CIFRI, titled “*Inland Small-Scale Fisheries in the Ganga River Basin: Transitioning from Vulnerability to Viability.*” The workshop brought

together fishers, fisheries department officials, researchers, and civil society representatives to collectively deliberate on the threats facing IMC fisheries and explore potential solutions.

Figure 1

Stakeholder interactions with riverine fishers during field visits in the Ganga River Basin, reflecting participatory engagement and experiential knowledge exchange.

Source: Authors' fieldwork

3. Theoretical and conceptual framework

The theoretical and conceptual framework is grounded in experiential and participatory learning approaches, as illustrated in Figure 1. The framework integrates stakeholder knowledge, field-based observation, and literature insights to build a comprehensive understanding of vulnerabilities and transition pathways in IMC fisheries. The process begins with an extensive literature survey to identify key issues and advances through concrete experiences involving direct engagement with stakeholders via interviews and focused group discussions. Subsequent phases emphasise reporting, knowledge sharing, and community validation, ensuring that local perceptions and experiential insights inform the conceptual synthesis. The final stage, reflective observation, employs participant observation and thematic analysis to interpret patterns and develop actionable strategies. This iterative and participatory design allows for the co-production of knowledge, linking theory with practice, and fostering a socially inclusive and ecologically grounded framework for sustainable fishery management in the Ganga Basin.

Figure 2

Experimental and participatory learning approach

4. Results and findings

4.1 IMC fisheries in the Ganga River

IMC catch trend: IMC production from the stretch of the river Ganga in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar has consistently been considered the principal fish production area over the past few years. The decadal IMC catches presented in Figure 2 reveal that IMC catches in 2022-2023 were 14.6 tonnes in Prayagraj, 4.09 tonnes in Varanasi, 1.84 tonnes in Buxar, and 3.55 tonnes in Patna. Since 2019, these four major landing centres have shown an overall increasing trend in IMC catches. However, historical records reveal a

concerning decline in the relative dominance of IMC in the Ganga River fishery. While Prayagraj and Buxar exhibit recent signs of recovery, Patna continues to experience a long-term decline. Furthermore, the shifting species composition underscores broader ecological changes within the river system.

Figure 3

Decadal changes in the landing of IMC in different sites

IMC seed production trends: Uttar Pradesh, recognised as one of the most important breeding grounds for IMCs and a key source of wild fish seed from the River Ganga, has witnessed a consistent decline in seed production over the decades. Spawn production, which was as high as 42.6 million in 1965, has steadily dropped with minor fluctuations, reaching only 5.3 million by 2018. This sharp decline (Figure 3) highlights the alarming depletion of natural IMC seed resources in the region, raising serious concerns for the sustainability of riverine carp fisheries.

Figure 4

IMC spawn production trend in Uttar Pradesh

4.2 Economic dependence of Ganga fishers on IMC

An assessment of fishers' income from IMC catches during 2022-23 reveals (Figure 4) distinct regional variations across the Ganga basin. Fishers in the middle stretch derived the highest share of income from IMC catches, followed by those in the lower stretch and then the upper stretch. IMCs contributed nearly 52% of the total fishing income, underscoring their central role in sustaining livelihoods. This heavy dependence on IMCs reflects both their cultural preference and economic importance, making their decline a direct threat to household income security and the long-term viability of small-scale fisheries in the Ganga.

Figure 5

Average annual income from IMC catches

4.3 Traditional IMC fishing in river Ganga

Indigenous Technical Knowledge Systems (ITKs) play a crucial role in traditional riverine fisheries, with one unique example being the ‘Tuka-feka’ hook-and-line fishery practised in the Buxar stretch of the River Ganga, selectively targeting IMCs such as *Labeo rohita*, *Labeo catla*, *Cirrhinus mrigala* and *Labeo calbasu* for their high economic value (Hornell, 1924; Ahmed, 1956; Jones, 1959; Saxena, 1964). The technique derives its name from “Tuka” (ball-shaped bait) and “Feka” (to throw). It involves the installation of bamboo-based H-shaped devices in shallow mid-channel waters during winter, with lines carrying small hooks (No. 4/0–5/0) embedded in handmade bait balls prepared from chickpea, mustard oil cake, jowar, mahua, fenugreek, rice, and local attractants like cardamom, camphor, *Karpur-kachari*, and *Sugandhabala* (*Elettaria cardamomum*, *Madhuca longifolia*, *Trigonella foenum*, and *Pavonia odorata*) (Sinha, 2002) (Figure 5). Occasionally, dolphin oil (*Platanista gangetica*) is also used, though this poses serious conservation concerns for the National Aquatic Animal (Sinha, 2002). The gear operates seasonally (February–May), with catch per unit effort ranging from 2.5 to 20 kg day⁻¹ and contributing ~0.25 tonnes of IMC landings annually at Buxar, although earlier decadal landings during the 1970s–1990s showed much higher carp dominance (Anon, 1970–1990). Despite its cultural significance, the method inadvertently targets IMCs during gonadal maturation (December–May), causing growth overfishing (Chondar, 1995; Jhingran and Pullin, 1985). Moreover, increasing dominance of exotics like common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) in the middle Ganga has shifted catch composition and reduced profitability, as IMCs fetch Rs. 300–350 kg⁻¹ compared to only Rs. 60–80 kg⁻¹ for common carp (Vass et al., 2010). Consequently, declining catches, ecological stress, and generational disinterest threaten the continuity of this ITK, suggesting that there must be documentation and conservation of such traditional practices before they fade into oblivion.

Figure 6*Schematic diagram of Tuka-Feka fishing*

4.4 Stakeholder dynamics in IMC fisheries governance

The stakeholder mapping (Table 1) highlights the complex, multi-layered governance challenges surrounding IMC fisheries in the Ganga River. IMCs are the backbone of riverine fisheries in northern and eastern India, carrying immense ecological, economic, and cultural value. Their recruitment, growth, and population stability depend on uninterrupted river flows, healthy spawning and nursery grounds, and good water quality. However, policy and infrastructure institutions disproportionately concentrate decision-making authority. These ecological conditions are shaped less by fisher communities themselves and more by powerful institutional actors such as the National Mission for Clean Ganga (NMCG), State Fisheries Departments, irrigation agencies, and hydropower authorities. These agencies hold significant authority over water releases, embankment construction, pollution control, and infrastructure development, as well as decisions that directly determine habitat connectivity, ecological flows, and ultimately, the sustainability of IMC stocks (CIFRI, 2020), yet fisheries concern often remain a secondary priority within their broader mandates of water management, flood control, or energy generation. This sectoral misalignment has far-reaching implications, weakening the natural replenishment cycles of IMCs and accelerating their decline (Dey et al., 2020; Sarkar, 2020).

On the other side of this governance equation are the traditional fisher communities, who rely most directly on IMC catches for their subsistence, nutrition, and cultural continuity. For these households, IMCs are not simply a commercial commodity; they represent a vital livelihood and a way of life. However, despite this deep dependence, fishers remain largely excluded from decisions that affect the health of IMC populations. Their voices are seldom heard in formal governance forums, and they continue to face barriers such as restricted access to institutional credit, exploitative market chains dominated by middlemen, and shrinking returns due to declining catch per unit effort (Sugunan, 1995; CIFRI, 2019). The result creates a paradox: those who are most invested in sustaining IMC fisheries are also the least empowered to influence policies that could safeguard them.

Between these poles lie intermediary actors, such as civil society organisations, research institutions, and academic bodies. These stakeholders contribute scientific knowledge on IMC breeding biology, stock status, and conservation requirements, and they also facilitate training and advocacy for fisher communities. However, limited funding and weak integration of research findings into policy frameworks often constrain their role (Nayak & Berkes, 2018). Market actors, including traders and wholesalers, exert additional but uneven influence. While they shape pricing systems and value-chain flows of IMCs, their focus typically rests on maximising short-term economic gains rather than long-term stock sustainability (FAO, 2021). At the periphery, secondary stakeholders such as consumers, pilgrims, and local municipal bodies exert indirect but significant pressures - whether through consumption demand, ritual practices, or unchecked pollution inputs into the river (MoEFCC, 2021).

Overall, this mapping exposes a deep governance gap in IMC fisheries management: the power to decide lies disproportionately with institutions focused on infrastructure and water allocation, while those most dependent on IMCs for survival are the fisher communities that remain structurally marginalised.

Stakeholder Category	Representative Actors	Relative Power/Influence	Level of Interest in IMC Fisheries	Nature of Stake / Potential Contribution
Policy and Regulatory Institutions	National Mission for Clean Ganga (NMCG) Ministry of Fisheries, Animal Husbandry & Dairying Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute (ICAR-CIFRI) State Fisheries Departments (U.P., Bihar, West Bengal, Jharkhand)	High Regulatory authority, financial allocation, research mandate	High Mandate to conserve riverine biodiversity, enhance fisheries production, and safeguard fisher livelihoods	Formulation and enforcement of policies, allocation of financial resources, scientific research on stock status, guidance on hatchery/restocking protocols, integration of fisheries into basin-wide Ganga River management plans
Water Resource and Infrastructure Authorities	Central Water Commission State Irrigation Departments NTPC and hydropower operators	High Control of water releases, dam/barrage operations, and dredging for navigation	Medium Fisheries conservation is peripheral to their primary mandates	Maintenance of ecological flows, mitigation of habitat fragmentation through fish passes, regulation of dredging and sand mining, and ensuring multi-

	Inland Waterways Authority of India (IWAI)			sectoral water allocation considers fisheries requirements
Primary Resource Users	Traditional fisher communities (e.g., Mallah, Nishad, Jalaha) Fisher cooperatives and Self-Help Groups (SHGs)	Medium Limited decision-making authority, but strong role in compliance and knowledge sharing	High Directly dependent on nutrition, livelihoods, and cultural identity	Day-to-day resource stewardship, indigenous ecological knowledge, adoption of sustainable gear and seasonal closure practices, participation in co-management frameworks
Civil Society and Knowledge Actors	Local and national NGOs (e.g., WWF-India, Toxics Link, Wetlands International) Academic and research institutions (universities, IITs, IISERs)	Medium Influence through advocacy, research evidence, and capacity building	High Interest in ecological sustainability, fisher welfare, and policy reform	Independent monitoring of fish stocks and habitats, community mobilisation, capacity building for fishers, and advocacy for biodiversity-friendly governance
Market and Value Chain Stakeholders	Fish traders and middlemen Wholesale markets (e.g., Kolkata, Patna) Cold storage operators and transporters	Medium Strong influence on pricing and market demand, but little direct involvement in conservation	Medium Concerned with supply consistency and consumer preference	Market incentives for sustainably harvested fish, promotion of eco-labeled IMC, integration into value-chain improvements (cold chain, fair pricing)
Secondary and Indirect Stakeholders	Urban consumers - Pilgrims and religious institutions (temple trusts, ghats) Riparian local governments (municipalities, panchayats)	Low Limited direct influence on management decisions	Low Fisheries are not central but linked to food security, cultural practices, and local economies	Demand-side awareness creation, adoption of sustainable consumption practices, support for clean river campaigns, reduction of household-level

				pollution and plastic input
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5. Vulnerability assessment of IMC

Drivers explain the changes in IMC fishery dynamics, shaping both resource availability and fisher livelihoods. These drivers were classified into key categories such as social, ecological, economic, and political to better understand their specific roles and interconnections in influencing the overall dynamics of IMC fisheries in the Ganga basin.

5.1 Social drivers

The social dimension is important for explaining the vulnerability of IMC fisheries in the Ganga River. Despite commanding the riverine fisheries, ancient fishing communities like Mallah, Nishad, and Jalaha have experienced extreme social ostracism. They are highly reliant on IMCs for food security, income generation, and cultural identity, yet have almost no role in the management decisions that affect fisheries and water distribution. This exclusion from institutional structures perpetuates inequity and undermines local stewardship of fishery resources.

The loss of traditional ecological knowledge systems, such as the Tuka-Feka technique, which was once crucial for sustainable IMC harvesting, is a significant social problem. Generational apathy, environmental deterioration, and competition from modern destructive forces have accelerated the disappearance of these time-tested traditions. As a result, fishing families' ability to adapt has gotten worse. Another important reason is that riverine fishers depend on IMCs for their livelihoods, as these species make up more than half of their entire fishing income. Social vulnerability has grown because of falling catches, changing market prices, and limited access to institutional financing. This situation has caused many fishermen to go into debt, move, or choose jobs that do not include fishing.

Insufficient literacy rates, little awareness of conservation regulations, and fragile organisational frameworks further impede opportunities for alternative revenue production or cooperative initiatives. Youth are increasingly disconnected from traditional fisheries due to low profitability and social shame, jeopardising the intergenerational transmission of knowledge and professions. The market system, which is characterised by intermediaries, perpetuates dependency and exploitation, resulting in negligible bargaining power for fishermen. Despite women's significant contributions to post-harvest handling and marketing, management discussions often overlook their positions, thereby perpetuating gender-based vulnerabilities.

5.2 Ecological drivers

The River Ganga's IMC fisheries are under mounting stress due to several ecological drivers. The delayed monsoon disrupts flood cycles, which usually synchronise with IMC spawning, due to a 56% decrease in rainfall across 133 districts of the basin, thereby reducing recruitment (Das et al., 2022). The growing dominance of exotic fish species adds further pressure, with the highest abundance recorded at Buxar (25.66%), an IMC-rich stretch; *Cyprinus carpio var. communis* (52.44%) and *Oreochromis niloticus* (40.37%) comprise the bulk of the exotic population, threatening native stock (Singh et al., 2025). Breeding ground depletion caused by sand mining, flow regulation, and habitat alteration has drastically reduced spawning sites, contributing to multi-decadal declines in IMC spawn availability (Swain et al., 2022). Water pollution, primarily from sewage and industrial effluents, degrades water quality by reducing dissolved oxygen and increasing toxins, which in turn heightens egg and larval mortality and weakens fish growth.

In addition, destructive fishing methods, such as blast/chemical fishing and the use of fine-mesh nets, result in high juvenile bycatch, egg and larval mortality, and habitat destruction, exacerbating recruitment failures and unsustainable harvest levels. Collectively, these ecological drivers severely undermine the resilience and sustainability of IMC fisheries in the River Ganga.

5.3 Political drivers

Construction of major barrages (e.g., Farakka Barrage) alters the natural flow regime of the Ganga, reducing dry season flows, altering hydrologic thresholds, and disrupting breeding and raising grounds for several Gangetic species. These changes diminish habitat connectivity, impede migration, and reduce spawn survival. River Linking Projects (RLP/Inter-Basin Transfers): large-scale river interlinking proposals threaten to disrupt aquatic ecosystems via changed flow regimes, altered sediment transport, potential spread of invasive species, and the drying of river stretches post-monsoon. These impacts can reduce habitat suitability for IMCs, lower recruitment and spawn availability, and modify fish community structure.

5.4 Economic drivers

The Ganga River recruitment pattern indicates overfishing. The current study revealed that overfishing occurs in the middle stretches of the Ganga, specifically targeting *L. rohita*. The estimated value of the exploitation ratio (E) was determined to be 0.58, somewhat higher than the ideal value (0.50). Diversifying livelihoods is a prominent economic driver, as is the declining decadal IMC fish catch (Ray et al., 2023). Important regions are prompting a shift towards alternative income sources, such as tourism, so fishing boats are gradually being converted into tourism boats in Varanasi and Allahabad.

6. Co-management for resilience of IMC fisheries

6.1 Existing enablers

IMC (Catla, Rohu, and Mrigal) are culturally preferred and nutritionally vital across the Ganga basin, where their high consumer demand ensures market stability and encourages continued fishing despite ecological decline. Studies confirm IMCs remain the dominant choice over exotic species, securing steady economic returns and premium prices 20–30% higher than common carp or tilapia in markets across Bihar and Uttar Pradesh (Sarkar et al., 2012; Pandit et al., 2019; Kelkar, 2021). This economic edge sustains fisher livelihoods even at reduced catch volumes, reinforcing IMCs' role as both a dietary staple and cultural symbol. The river's geomorphology, floodplains, oxbow lakes, and shallow stretches naturally support their breeding and recruitment, particularly in middle Ganga stretches such as Varanasi and Patna, where monsoonal hydrology aligns with spawning cycles (Dwivedi et al., 2014; Kelkar, 2021).

At the governance and community level, targeted interventions further strengthen IMC sustainability (Figure 6). ICAR-CIFRI and Namami Gange have led awareness and sensitisation campaigns that have improved fishers' understanding of destructive practices, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable harvesting. Field evidence shows sensitised fishers are more likely to adopt selective gears and comply with seasonal bans (Datta et al., 2016). Complementing this, large-scale river ranching programs under Namami Gange and CIFRI annually release millions of hatchery-reared IMC fingerlings into the Ganga, with early signs of improved catches in stocked areas (Saini et al., 2024). Together, consumer preference, supportive river topography, substantial market value, fisher awareness, and replenishment initiatives form a multi-faceted support system for sustaining IMC populations, even amid ecological and governance challenges.

Figure 7

Existing viable opportunities for IMC fisheries

6.2 Responses to existing enablers

Addressing the vulnerabilities of IMC fisheries in the Ganga River requires a multifaceted set of ecological, institutional, and socio-economic responses (Table 2). Collectively, these responses highlight the importance of integrated strategies that combine ecological restoration, technological innovation, market support, and community empowerment to ensure the long-term viability of IMC fisheries in the Ganga River system.

Dimension	Key response strategies	Examples / Evidence	Expected outcome
Ecological	Maintenance of environmental flows (e-flows)	Sarkar <i>et al.</i> (2012); NMCG (2018)	Improved spawning, migration, and recruitment of IMCs
	River ranching and stock enhancement programs	Namami Gange, ICAR-CIFRI, Saini <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Restored fish stock and biodiversity recovery

	<p>Wetland restoration (mauns, chaus, beels)</p>	<p>Jhingran & Sugunan (1990); Sarkar <i>et al.</i> (2012)</p>	<p>Enhanced nursery habitats and ecosystem services</p>
<p>Regulatory & Technological</p>			
	<p>Drone-based surveillance and monitoring</p>	<p>Pilot projects in inland fisheries</p>	<p>Deterrence of destructive fishing (dynamite/poison)</p>
	<p>Long-term ecological monitoring (DO, pH, pollutants)</p>	<p>Singh <i>et al.</i> (2019)</p>	<p>Improved data-driven management and adaptive responses</p>
<p>Socio-economic</p> <p>Reduced post-harvest losses and higher market value</p>			
	<p>Promotion of value addition through cooperatives</p>	<p>Datta <i>et al.</i> (2010)</p>	<p>Diversified income and livelihood resilience</p>
	<p>Training and sensitization programs</p>	<p>Ongoing under Namami Gange & CIFRI</p>	<p>Empowered and skilled fishing communities</p>

Figure 8

Socio-ecological transition framework for IMC fisheries

Figure 9

Ranching, awareness and sensitisation on biodiversity conservation

7. Emerging threats to IMC fisheries

The fisheries of Indian major carp in the Ganga Basin are increasingly challenged by a complex combination of ecological, hydrological, and anthropogenic factors (Das et al., 2013; Bhakta et al., 2018). The natural breeding and recruitment of IMCs have encountered considerable disruption due to river flow regulation, habitat fragmentation, and the loss of floodplain connectivity caused by dams and barrages (Lakra et al., 2011; Bhakta et al., 2018). Industrial effluents, agricultural runoff, and domestic sewage are significant factors in the deterioration of water quality, subsequently affecting fish health and their reproductive success (Sarkar et al., 2012). The over-extraction of resources and the use of damaging fishing techniques exacerbate the reduction of fish populations, while the introduction of invasive species such as

silver carp and common carp has led to ecological competition and genetic intermingling (Sugunan, 1995; Das et al., 2021). Moreover, variations in climate, including erratic rainfall and rising water temperatures, have influenced fish phenology and productivity trends (Das et al., 2013). The intricate nature of these threats requires a thorough strategy for management interventions aimed at reinstating the ecological balance of the Ganga River system.

Category	Key threats	Examples/impacts
Hydrological modifications	Barrages, dams, and flow regulation	Blocked migration routes; reduced spawning success
Pollution	Industrial effluents, domestic sewage, agricultural runoff	Habitat degradation; fish kills
Overfishing	Unregulated and destructive fishing methods	Juvenile depletion; biodiversity loss
Exotic species invasion	Silver carp, grass carp, common carp	Competition and genetic dilution
Climate change	Temperature rise, erratic monsoon, floods	Habitat alteration; disease emergence
Institutional weaknesses	Fragmented governance; weak enforcement	Poor data management; lack of accountability

8. Way forward

The fieldwork and stakeholder dialogues raise several critical questions that demand further research and participatory action to ensure the long-term viability of IMC fisheries in the Ganga Basin:

- *Ecological & hydrological flows*: What are the long-term impacts of barrages, river-linking projects, and reduced monsoonal flows on IMC recruitment and spawning habitats? How can e-flow policies be enforced to align water management with fisheries sustainability?
- *Governance and equity*: How can fisher communities most dependent yet least empowered be meaningfully included in decision-making processes currently dominated by infrastructure and policy institutions?
- *Invasive and destructive practices*: How will the rising dominance of exotic species and destructive fishing (e.g., zero nets, poison, dynamite) reshape IMC stock dynamics, and what innovative enforcement or community-led alternatives can reverse these trends?
- *Socio-economic transitions*: Can alternative livelihoods such as tourism and aquaculture coexist with traditional fishing without deepening conflicts or accelerating resource overexploitation?
- *Market and value chains*: How can market interventions (cold chain infrastructure, eco-labelling, value-added products) be scaled up to secure fair incomes for fishers while incentivising sustainable harvests?
- *Technological & Monitoring Tools*: What role can innovations such as drone surveillance, real-time water quality monitoring, and fisher cooperatives play in strengthening ecological compliance and stock enhancement?

These questions underscore that IMC fisheries cannot be sustained through ecological or technical measures alone; they require participatory co-management, adaptive governance, and integration of fisher knowledge with policy frameworks. The future of IMCs in the Ganga will be determined by choices made today by communities, institutions, and policymakers working in concert toward a viable, equitable, and ecologically sound river system.

9. Conclusions

IMC fisheries in the Ganga River represent a living socio-ecological system, continually shaped by ecological, hydrological, economic, and institutional forces. While IMCs remain culturally preferred, nutritionally vital, and economically valuable, their populations have been declining due to habitat loss, flow regulation, pollution, invasive species, and destructive fishing. Fisher communities display remarkable resilience through adaptation and cooperation, yet their vulnerabilities are intensified by structural marginalisation, weak governance, and market asymmetries. Emerging interventions such as sensitisation programs, mesh-size regulations, river ranching, e-flow releases, and wetland restoration offer important pathways to recovery. However, sustaining IMCs demands inclusive governance, adaptive policy, and cross-sectoral collaboration to balance ecological imperatives with fisher livelihoods.

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The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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